

SPECIFICITY, MECHANISMS AND TEACHING OF CEFR IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) is the most comprehensive, and the most widely used set of foreign language education standards throughout the world. The recent reforms in foreign language teaching in Uzbekistan have mainly touched upon teaching English language in all levels and stages of education. At this point CEFR plays as the main framework to be adopted in developing the national standard. In this article, we shall discuss reforms of adoption and implementation of the new standard which was a requirement of time and has started a new era in the whole system of foreign languages learning in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: CEFR, teaching, learning, assessment, CEFR levels, education, stages of education, foreign language.

INTRODUCTION

The beginning of 2000's marked a new era in foreign languages teaching in Uzbekistan when all stakeholders including teachers, students, schools, colleges, lyceums and universities started to feel the changes in the way of foreign languages were taught and learned. (Jalolov 2015). In order to provide effective higher education, Uzbekistan accepted significant reforms by performing use of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) and National Qualifications Framework (NQF) in the country. CEFR standards provide effective learning of foreign language EFL classes. Both projects will take part in the implementation of Presidential Decree № 1875 of December of 2012 in enhancement of the teaching and learning of foreign languages in order to strengthen the communication skills and international effect of future Uzbekistan specialists in all fields.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Overview of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages The Common European Framework of Reference for Languages, which is commonly referred as CEFR (Council of Europe, 2001) is considered as an innovative language policy document designed and developed by the language policy division of the Council of Europe in the 1990s. The CEFR facilitates cooperation among various educational institutions and educational and other stakeholders around the world, moreover, providing easier mobility opportunities for professionals and common citizens across countries (Council of Europe, 2001). Goullier (2007) and North (2007) suggest that the CEFR is a

descriptive document, rather than a prescriptive document. In other words it refers and can be used with all languages and its primary goal is to enhance language practitioners’ reflections on their specific educational and geographical contexts, language learners and language teaching objectives. According to North (2007, p. 656) the CEFR is defined as a “concertina-like reference tool, not an instrument to be applied”. Therefore, it should be referred, consulted and adapted depending on the needs and realities of a definite local area rather than blindly followed as a set of concrete unchangeable and discrete rules. It was published online in 1996 and in 2001 it was introduced in a paper version.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since its gaining popularity around world the CEFR document has been translated into 39 languages and has been used and/or referred by a number of countries around the world for the development and introduction of foreign language policies, including Uzbekistan. As it is declared by the Council of Europe the main purpose of the CEFR is the alignment of language learning, teaching, assessment and testing and ultimately guarantee correlation of learning outcomes across languages, contexts and countries. The document “provides a common basis for the elaboration of language syllabuses, curriculum guidelines, examinations, textbooks, etc.” (Council of Europe, 2001 p1). The development of the CEFR coincided with fundamental changes in language teaching, with the move away from the grammar-translation method to communicative approach. That is to say, the document is considered to act as a tool that can “be used to analyze L2 learners’ needs, specify L2 learning goals, guide the development of L2 learning materials and activities, and provide orientation for the assessment of L2 learning outcomes” (Little, 2006, p167), and in coherent and comprehensible way. The CEFR 1 - depicts competencies language learners need to form to be an effective language user; 2 - it suggests sets of “can do” descriptors that point out what learners can do when they reach a certain competency in a definite proficiency level; 3 - it offers instructional guiding principles on how to teach and assess learners competencies; 4 - it offers a common reference level scales for the comparability and recognition of language competences across contexts and countries.

The CEFR provides a reference point for language competency around the world as in the Table N1:

Global CEFR scale	General Level	TOEFL (ICT)	Cambridge ESOL	IELTS Level
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				Level	
Proficient User	C2	Advanced		CPE	IELTS 7-8
	C1	Upper-Intermediate	233-270	CAE/BEC/Higher	IELTS 6-7
Independent User	B2	Intermediate/Upper Intermediate	152-213	FCE/BEC Vantage	IELTS 5-6
	B1	Pre-Intermediate	100-133	PET/BEC Preliminary	IELTS 4
Basic User	A2	Elementary	40-85	KET	IELTS 3
	A1	Beginner	-	Starters, Movers, Flyers	IELTS 0-2

CONCLUSION

Uzbekistan has already established teaching English language in all levels and stages of education based on CEFR as the main framework to be adopted in developing the national standard. Graduate learners of Uzbekistan educational system who are able to communicate as fluently and proficiently as possible in English so that language communication skills make them more employable and better to undertake further study and research in their further career.

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